

INTEGRATION SKILLS IN PEDAGOGY

Jabborova Dilafruz Ismatullo kizi

Teacher, Karshi engineering and economics Institute

Foreign languages department

jabborovadilafrozl995@2mail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7189900>

Integration is a relatively new approach in pedagogy, the introduction of which can increase the level of the educational process the rising generation. Integration in pedagogy and education is, first of all, the interaction of various elements of any systems in order to obtain something holistic, new. The concept of "system" in modern pedagogy can be used in different aspects, for example: educational institution as a system; educational system classes; the system of relationships between learners and teachers, etc.

Integration in pedagogy is traditionally considered in two aspects:

1) as a state for which consistency is characteristic, orderliness and stability of links between various elements;

2) as a process that leads to a given state. Thus, integration in pedagogy is a very important indicator of the effectiveness of the entire education system; it serves as a criterion for its integrity.

The interaction of various elements in the educational process - this process is quite complex and multi-level. In connection with these pedagogy, there are different approaches to the definition of the concept integration. Integration is the highest form relationship, expressing the unity of all elements that make up the system education and its content.

Integrated skills focuses on the four main English skills - reading, writing, speaking and listening - through a "Communicative Language Teaching" methodology. New grammar patterns are learned in the context of a conversation or a real-life situation. Students will engage in various activities to practice English including listening tasks, role playing, and stimulating discussions.

Perhaps teachers and administrators think it is logistically easier to present courses on writing divorced from speaking, or on listening isolated from reading. They may believe that it is instructionally impossible to concentrate on more than one skill at a time [1].

Even if it were possible to fully develop one or two skills in the absence of all the others, such an approach would not ensure adequate preparation for later success in academic communication, career-related language use, or everyday interaction in the language. An extreme example is the grammar-translation method, which teaches students to analyze grammar and to translate (usually in

writing) from one language to another. This method restricts language learning to a very narrow, noncommunicative range that does not prepare students to use the language in everyday life.

Teach language learning strategies and emphasize that a given strategy can often enhance performance in multiple skills [3].

All elements in the education system serve the same purpose – all-round development of the learner, they contribute to the satisfaction of their interests and abilities, ensure coordination of influence on motivational, emotional, effective-practical and volitional areas of the learner's personality. Thus, summarizing all that has been said, we can say that the concept of "integration" in pedagogy means: characterization of the goals of education, a combination of pedagogical means, applied, both in educational and extracurricular activities, integrity in achieving planned results, the relationship between the main and additional education, flexibility in the organization of educational activities, using various methods and forms of extracurricular activities; creation of creative circles, as well as the introduction of integrative courses, interaction of all elements of the educational process.

The priority task of influencing the learner in the learning process is to prepare him for the perception of the surrounding reality, as a single whole. In other words, students should consider the relationship between objects and phenomena before drawing the big picture.

In addition, the learner must be able to perceive phenomena from different angles. The effectiveness learner's cognitive activity depends on certain conditions, including the fact of applying integration in pedagogy.

There are different types of integrations in pedagogy. Intra-subject implies integration within any separate taken discipline. At the same time, separate, disparate concepts and facts from one area of knowledge are combined into a system. Thus, educational the material is built in the form of large blocks. This form integration to receive complete information on the studied material. The lesson is more capacious. Intra-subject integration involves the construction of a spiral structure in the presentation of the material.

At the same time, the process of assimilation of the new proceeds both from the general to the particular, and vice versa. The teacher presents new information in portions, which gradually helps to deepen, as well as increase the already existing horizons of the student in to this subject. Modern pedagogy speaks of maintaining educational process through consolidation and simultaneous study related to each other various themes and subjects. And also the student it is proposed to link or generalize among themselves some exercises

and assignments received, the implementation of independent actions on the basis of analogy, induction, comparison, development of the necessary tables, graphs, diagrams or other schematic representations.

Intra-system integration is another type of integration. It is characterized by the fact that students develop the ability to use the material of one subject in the study of another. Child acquire knowledge in a complex way, perceiving general scientific categories and approaches as a whole. Here integration can be done different ways. The first of them - horizontal - sets interdisciplinary connections based on the same scientific knowledge. It avoids repetition and saves study time. Another approach respectively vertical. It is characterized by the fact that interdisciplinary connections serve to form similar types of thinking, for example, humanitarian-environmental, physical-mathematical, etc.

In addition, "integration" in pedagogy is also subdivided according to the form to internal and external. Internal integration is characteristic of internal educational process. External - carried out with interaction of an educational institution with other structures and with society.

Internal, or intra-school, integration is the relationship of various pedagogical tools used in several levels:

- establishing internal communications (for example, intra-subject);
- interaction between educational means (for example, between objects);
- connection of material one subject to the study of another (conducting an integrated lesson);
- introduction of new teaching aids (conducting classes in groups of different ages, etc.).

The effectiveness of the learning process is enhanced by several not a few important factors, namely:

- an increase in various educational functions in the classroom, which will serve as growth moral qualities in learners, as well as influence social development; increasing the cognitive, mental element during extracurricular activities;

- the use of various auxiliary, namely educational means that help not to distinguish between educational and extra-curricular activities of the student, but rather bring into a single whole, which serves to ensure the all-round development of the individual. All this possible with a well-built integrated approach.

To implement a comprehensive impact on the formation personality, it is necessary to develop a multi-level model of interaction, which provides for different stages of growing up of learners.

Integration in pedagogy implies the interaction of various elements of any system in order to getting something whole. Integration is noticed in two aspects: as a state and as a process. Integration happens intra-subject and intra-system. The shape distinguishes between external and internal integration.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Scarcella R. & Oxford R., 1992. "The tapestry of language learning: The individual in the communicative classroom". Boston: Heinle & Heinle.
2. Ergasheva N.N. Raising motivation of students in a second/foreign language acquisition. [Electronic Resource]. Questions of science and education, No. 5 (50), 2019. P. 168-171. URL: https://scientificpublication.ru/images/PDF/2019/50/Questions_of_science_and_education-5-50.pdf/ (date of access: 10/15/2019).
3. Khamdamova S.O. The effectiveness of the use of multimedia and hypermedia in English classes. [Electronic Resource]. Questions of science and education, 2018. S. 89-91. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/v/effektivnost-ispolzovaniya-multimedia-i-gipermedia-na-zanyatiah-angliyskogo-yazyka/> (date of access: 10/15/2019).